

Thermal Studies of Copper(II) Monohydroxychalcones

P. G. MUNDHE*, P. B. DEOGAONKAR and R. A. BHOBE

J. E. S. College, Jalna-431 203

Manuscript received 20 May 1997, revised 2 December 1997, accepted 2 January 1998

Monohydroxychalcones of the type $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(2\text{-OH-MHC})_2$ and $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(2'\text{-OH-5'-Cl-MHC})_2$ have been prepared and subjected to thermal analysis on the 4-function MOM-Q-derivatograph. A detailed mathematical and graphical treatment yield the thermodynamic and kinetic parameters.

Unsaturated ketones are gaining importance as reactive intermediates and are used to obtain the biologically important heterocycles. This class of compounds exhibits wide spectrum of pharmaceutical¹ and biological^{2,3} properties. It has been shown that the prime cause of these activities is the presence of α,β -unsaturated ketonic system⁴. The bacteriostatic activity is enhanced by the substitution of halogen and hydroxyl groups^{3,5} in the chalcones. Therefore, the study of halogen and hydroxy substituted chalcones is of great importance.

Literature survey reveals lack of work on the thermal studies of the complexes of the chalcones with transition metals. However, the kinetics of thermal decomposition, activation energies and apparent activation energies of some metal complexes have been studied by some workers⁶. Hence, it was thought worthwhile to convert the substituted chalcones into their respective transition metal complexes and investigate their thermodynamic and kinetic parameters using thermal analysis technique.

Theoretical

The fraction of total mass decomposed (α) is given as

$$\alpha = \frac{W_0 - W_t}{W_0 - W_r}$$

where, W_0 is the initial weight of the compound, W_t the weight at t and W_r the weight of residue at the completion of heating.

The $g(\alpha)$ values were calculated⁷ as

$$g(\alpha) = \frac{1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1-n}}{(1-n)} \quad (1)$$

where, n is the order of reaction. The order of reaction and the E_a values were evaluated by Freeman and Carroll method⁸ (E_a from slope and n from intercept). The final plots were

$$\frac{\Delta \log (dW/dt)}{\Delta \log W_r} \text{ vs } \frac{\Delta (1/T)}{\Delta \log W_r}$$

Results and Discussion

The basic equation⁹ used for calculating kinetic parameters from thermal plot of mass loss vs time/temp. (ϕ , the heating rate being constant) is

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = (A/\phi) (1-\alpha)^n \exp (-E/RT) \quad (2)$$

where, A is the preexponential term and the other symbols have the usual meaning. This equation has been modified as

$$\log \left[\frac{g(\alpha)}{T^3} \right] = \log \left[\frac{kR}{h\phi E} \right] + \frac{\Delta S}{2.303 R} - \frac{E}{2.303 RT} \quad (3)$$

A plot of $\log g(\alpha)/T^3$ vs $1/T$ should yield a straight-line and from the intercept ΔS value is calculated. Such plots are not shown but the values are given in Table 1. Eyring's well-known equations were used to evaluate ΔF values (Table 2).

TABLE 1—EQUATIONS OF STRAIGHT-LINES FOR E_a VALUES (LEAST-SQUARE METHOD)

Compd.	Expression A^*T	Expression B^*T
$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-2'-MHC}$	$-2622.9 - 4.35 T$	$-4250 + 12.32 T$
$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-2',5'-Cl-MHC}$	$-1739.1 - 6.04 T$	$-4666 + 13.13 T$

$A^* = \log [g(\alpha)/T^3]$; $B^* = -\ln [d\alpha/dT]$

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR Cu^{II} COMPOUNDS OF MHC

Compd.	$E_a (\Delta H)$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^*$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔF^* kJ mol ⁻¹
$[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(2\text{-OH-MHC})_2]$	65.54	193.00	123.40
$[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(2\text{-OH-5-Cl-MHC})_2]$	72.52	224.50	139.80

* At 300 K.

Since the object of the present work was to extract as much information as possible from the mass-loss vs temp/time curves for the MHC complexes of copper(II) and since the curves obtained were well-defined, of large dimensions amenable to accurate and lilliputian measurements, the authors thought of deriving Z , the frequency factor by using the expression¹⁰,

$$\log \frac{Z E_a}{Rq} = \log g(\alpha) - \log p(x) \quad (4)$$

where, the term $\log p(x)$ is defined in detail in literature¹⁰ and ready-made values of which picked up from Doyle's Tables¹¹ were used according to the procedure given by Zsako¹². The values of Z were easily calculated (Table 3) as all other values, namely, q , E_a , R and B [$= \log g(\alpha) - \log p(x)$] were accurately known.

The 'apparent activation energy' ($S^\#$) was then calculated from the expression,

TABLE 3—PARAMETERS FOR KINETICS OF DECOMPOSITION

Compd.	α_{av}	$-\log P(x)$	B	Z	$-S^\#$ J mol ⁻¹	A
[Cu ^{II} -(2-OH-MHC) ₂]	0.5730	7.5980	7.5279	3.56×10^2	101.70	5.78×10^3
[Cu ^{II} -(2-OH-5-Cl-MHC) ₂]	0.5487	7.0750	6.9757	90.32	108.10	1.55×10^4

$$S^\# = 2.303 \log \frac{Zh}{kT^*} \quad (5)$$

where, T^* was taken as K at which the weight-loss of the complex was half the total loss (T^* for Cu^{II}-2'-OH-MHC and Cu^{II}-2',5'-Cl-MHC were 621 and 719 K respectively), the justification for such procedure being given¹². These values for the two complexes are given in Table 3.

Evaluation of the preexponential term (A): The basic equation given in (eqn. 2) can be modified as

$$\ln \frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \ln [A/\phi] + n \ln (1-\alpha) - E/RT \quad (6)$$

where, α is the 'average value' as listed in Table 3. The linear plots of $-\ln [d\alpha/dt]$ vs $1/T$ yielded the intercept $\ln [A/\phi] + n \ln (1-\alpha)$, where n values were obtained from the plots of

$$\frac{\Delta \log (dw/dt)}{\Delta \log W_r} \text{ vs } \frac{\Delta (1/T)}{\Delta \log W_r}$$

the values being given in Table 4 (private communication from P. D. Jadhav and RAB) and ϕ being 5°/min. The A values then could be easily deduced (Table 3). From the values of A and Z thus obtained, P , the probability or steric factors, were deduced for Cu^{II}(2'-MHC) and Cu^{II}(2',5'-chloro MHC) as 16.23 and 1.72×10^2 respectively.

The DTG is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1.

The prominent DTG peaks are listed in Table 5. It is seen that for simple MHC complex of copper, the peaks number only two whereas due to chloro influence in the ligand, the DTG peaks of Cu^{II}-2',5'-Cl-MHC complex in-

crease to some eight well-defined ones. However, in both the complexes, the peaks at 613 and 833 are common, indicating that these are due to pure MHC ligand decomposing.

TABLE 4

$\frac{\Delta \log (dw/dt)}{\Delta \log W_r}$	$\frac{\Delta (1/T)}{\Delta \log W_r}$	
Cu ^{II} -2'-MHC		
2.8412	1.21	
2.9826	1.24	
3.1604	1.28	$E_a = 65.54 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$
3.5710	1.38	
4.3601	1.60	$n = 1.38$
5.3190	1.88	
Cu ^{II} -2',5'-Cl-MHC		
2.7954	1.10	
3.0816	1.14	
3.3828	1.23	$E_a = 72.52 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$
3.6609	1.28	
4.8479	1.61	$n = 1.25$

TABLE 5—DTG PEAK TEMPERATURES (K) OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Peak no.	Peak temp. K
[Cu ^{II} -(2-OH-MHC) ₂]	1	613
	2	833
[Cu ^{II} -(2-OH-5-Cl-MHC) ₂]	1	543
	2	613
	3	683
	4	783
	5	833
	6	873
	7	893
	8	913

In general, it is noticed that the chloro group introduced in the MHC ligand raises the E_a (~75.34 kJ mol⁻¹) as also the steric hindrance (~170 for the chloro whereas only ~17 for the simple and purer MHC complex of Cu^{II}). Even the decomposition of the chloro complex is more orderly (ΔS^\ddagger ~225.00 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹). The α_{av} values which indicate the decomposition at time t per total decomposition at infinite time, is much slower in chloro complex, presumably because the ligand is held more tightly than the purer 2-OH MHC, chloro group being virtually an electron sink.

Experimental

2-Hydroxychalcone: The oily mass formed from the reaction of phenol (30 g) and acetic anhydride (30 ml) was extracted with ether. Phenyl acetate (20 g) thus obtained was mixed with anhydrous AlCl₃ and dry pyridine (20 ml) and the mixture was heated to 120–160° and then decomposed with HCl. 2-Hydroxyacetophenone produced at this stage was added to benzaldehyde (0.02 mol) to get 2-

hydroxychalcone. 2-Hydroxy-5-chlorochalcone was obtained in an identical manner except that instead of phenol, *p*-chlorophenol was used.

Copper(II) complexes : Reaction of aqueous copper(II) acetate (A.R.) with a slight excess of the respective chalcones in alcohol resulted in the precipitation of complexes after prolonged shaking. Estimation of copper was done by thiocyanate method, weighing as $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})_2](\text{SCN})_2$.

The complexes gave satisfactory C, H and Cu analyses.

Thermograms and DTG of the sample (0.185 g) were taken on a MOM-Q-derivatograph and were reduced to 1/6th of the original size. The heating rate was 5°/min.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge Head of Chemistry Department, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad, for allowing them to carry the thermal work at the departmental laboratories.

References

1. R. F. DEVITT, A. TIMONEY, and M. A. VICKAR, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 4941; J. KOO, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1964, **53**, 1329; D. DONNELLY and R. GEOGHEGGER, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, **8**, 872.
2. S. C. KUSHAWA, DINKAR, and J. B. LAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 82; K. P. JADHAV and D. B. INGLE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1983, **22**, 150; R. A. MANE, V. H. PATIL, and D. B. INGLE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1978, **16**, 1114.
3. Y. S. AGASIMUDDIN and S. D. JOLDD, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, **3**, 220.
4. W. B. GEIGER and J. E. CONN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 112.
5. E. SCHRAUFSTATTER and S. DEUTCH, *Naturforsch. Teil B*, 1948, **3**, 163.
6. P. C. SRIVASTAVA, B. N. SINGH, S. K. GHOSH, and N. C. GANGULY, *J. Therm. Anal.*, 1986, **31**, 1153; B. D. HEDA and P. V. KHADIKAR, *Chim. Belg.*, 1980, **89**, 331; M. E. BROWN and G. M. SALLOWE, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1981, **49**, 333; LINKESOVE, MARIA, LANGFELDEROVA, and HELENA, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1985, **92**, 125.
7. A. W. COATS and J. P. REDFERN, *Nature*, 1964, **68**, 201.
8. E. S. FREEMAN and B. CARROLL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, **62**, 394.
9. L. REICH and D. W. LEVI, *Macromol. Rev.*, 1967, **1**, 177.
10. J. ZASCO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 2407.
11. C. D. DOYLE, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 1961, **15**, 285.
12. J. ZSAKO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 2409.